

DOCUMENTATION AND CONSERVATION PLANNING

IN MANUSCRIPT COLLECTIONS

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Introduction: Valuable manuscripts in library collections are artifacts of cultural heritage with their documentary characteristics and artistic values. Libraries, besides being institutions that enable the society to benefit from these artifacts, also have an important mission to transfer them to future generations. For this purpose, it is the responsibility of the institution to prepare a long-term protection plan and medium in which this plan will be implemented under the right conditions. There are digital media such as “collection management databases” where the information obtained during the documentation phase are examined. These are excellent tools for managing data for conservation planning. The data that are collected during documentation should be recorded in easily accessible, maintainable, classification and sorting programs.

The application of these features in the data will provide information that will guide the conservation planning. The data that are classified in the long term and the information expressing the problems of the library will be converted into graphics and the results will be reflected in the reports with concrete expressions. In this way, it is possible to carry out a planned conservation work after determining the order of priority. As a result of planning that is not done in line with concrete data, a priority problem is likely to be overlooked.

Manuscript Condition- Documentation Form and its content

In the content of the "Manuscript Condition- Documentation Form" prepared for an artifact in the studies carried out by the Conservation and Restoration Laboratory, there is a lot of information from the manufacture technique of the artifact to its historical importance. It has been summarized below that these titles and information are roughly in the form of data.

In a manuscript condition- documentation form, first of all, the inventory information of the work is included. In addition, a high-resolution photograph of the general view before and after the treatment is placed on the form. Technical details are sometimes included in the report with photographs and sometimes with figures. Information such as the technical structure of the manuscript in terms of binding features, ornamentation features, and back stitching are noted. Regarding the text part of the manuscript, information is given about the features of the paper and the features of the decoration in the text. In the Damages section, depending on the structural elements of the book, observations made on each subject, including the volume, text, sewing, shiraze and old repairs, are included.

It should be mentioned that the suggested conservation practices will be applied in order to reverse the damage(s) on the artifact. Every practice, including application stages, materials and devices, is recorded. It is very important for planning to note the start and end date of the conservation. This information will help us to estimate the cost and time of similar practice in the future.

Deterioration degrees:

GOOD / MEDIUM / BAD / MISSING / RENEWED

Libraries set annual, 5-year and longer-term targets depending on the number of works, the conservation staff working and the laboratory facilities, depending on the average number of works they fulfill per year. Strategies to achieve these goals and the creation of protection and restoration policies should be discussed and decided in the commissions, which will be attended by all the personnel who will work in this field.

The most important data sources in determining these strategies are the results obtained from the documentation studies. For example, if the data obtained from annual and 5-year reports show that most of the artifacts are damaged due to moisture, we will be informed that there is an architectural and/or technical problem in the library that is a source of moisture. Or the type of damage detected on the spines of the books will give a clue about the information that the books were stored or handled incorrectly. The most important tool for us to obtain this information will be the recording of the data with a correct program.

It is very important that the information in the documentation forms, that is, the titles selected from the data as research subjects, have the feature of being turned into a list by withdrawing from the form. In this way, it will be possible to obtain statistical results from the data. It is known that the data of Pre-Treatment Report form provides great benefits to scientific studies. Establishing a correlation between the manufacture technique and the detected deterioration process is only possible with statistical data. After proving that there is a correlation between the two values with numerical data, a project can be started in which experimental studies and appropriate method research will be carried out. While preparing the report for planning, the conservation department will also be able to instantly prepare a due diligence report covering the entire collection with the data it will receive from the database.

Observation results evaluating the physical stability and appearance of the books in the library are available in the manuscript condition documentation form. The books evaluated during the visual examination; The conditions of the cover, back, binding seam and side papers were noted. As the evaluation criteria, 5 levels were taken as bad, fair, good, missing and renewed. The data obtained as a result of the study are given in Table 1 below. The data obtained from this study also enabled cost calculations on issues such as consumables to be purchased in the coming years, additional labor force, and the competence of laboratory facilities.

	Bad	Fine	Good	Missing	Renewed
COVER	18%	36%	32%	4%	10%
SPINE	32%	30%	24%	4%	10%
BINDING	13%	17%	61%	-	9%
SIDE PAGE	13%	18%	40%	-	9%

Table 1: Book binding damage condition results in the collection

Result

It is no longer sufficient to store the information obtained by examining each work in pdf format and printed paper. It may be possible to obtain numerical results by compiling the data obtained in short-term studies. However, making evaluations from the data obtained at the end of 20-30 years of work will become more difficult with each passing year. Failure to define large-scale problems causes institutions to develop wrong strategies and face new problems. However, it is possible to save the data obtained by using the right methods in the library collections in the right computer programs and to obtain efficient results from the protection and repair applications applied in line with the problems to be extracted from these data.

Reference

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